

Nature's benefits and burdens: Integrating ecosystem (dis)services into Nepal's conservation policies

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Introduction

Ecosystem services—the benefits that nature provides to people—have gained increasing attention in global policy discussions due to their potential to address urgent environmental challenges such as biodiversity loss and habitat degradation, while also supporting human well-being (Pu et al., 2023). These concepts now underpin major international frameworks, including the Convention on Biological Diversity's Aichi Targets (2010–2020), the Sustainable Development Goals (2015–2030), and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (2022–2050).

Milestone initiatives like the 2005 Millennium Ecosystem Assessment and the 2010 The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity study further helped mainstream ecosystem services into global policy agendas (Costanza et al., 2014). In Nepal, research shows that conservation policies have been shaped by these global trends (Chaudhary & McGregor, 2018). However, despite this influence, the extent to which ecosystem services—and disservices, the negative impacts of nature—are integrated into national conservation policies remains poorly understood. Most existing studies focus only on the benefits of nature, often overlooking disservices that also shape public perception and management decisions.

To address this gap, our study reviewed 111 policy and legal documents related to Nepal's protected areas—including acts, regulations, policies, strategies, and directives—and incorporated insights from 19 expert interviews (Subedi et al., 2025). This policy brief presents the key findings from that study and present

practical recommendations to inform policymakers and support more inclusive and effective biodiversity conservation in Nepal.

Key messages

Our study examining how well Nepal's protected areas policies address ecosystem services—the benefits nature provides—and disservices—the negative impacts of nature—was conducted through a review of 111 policy and legal documents, supported by 19 expert interviews. The findings reveal that ecosystem (dis)services are implicitly acknowledged but explicitly overlooked in existing policies. This policy brief shares key recommendations from that study to meaningfully integrate ecosystem (dis)services into the protected areas governance:

- Explicitly incorporate ecosystem (dis)services into the core policies governing protected areas;
- Promote non-monetary assessment of ecosystem (dis)services in the protected areas
- Formalize the provision of carbon sequestration services;
- Discourage commercial conservation models that marginalize local and indigenous communities; and,
- Establish a national ecosystem accounting system based on the UN System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA) Ecosystem Accounting Framework.

Research insights and evidence

The findings indicate that ecosystem (dis)services are largely embedded implicitly within Nepal's protected area policies. This is evident in provisions related to traditional use rights, tourism regulation, biodiversity conservation, and human-wildlife conflict mitigation. However, explicit recognition is gradually emerging (Table 1). While a few recent policies incorporate the

concept of ecosystem services, foundational policy frameworks like the National Parks and Wildlife Conservation Act (1973), its regulations (1974), and other regulations governing national parks and wildlife reserves still lack clear definitions or valuation methods.

Table 1. Definitions, categories, and valuation of ecosystem (dis)services in the policy frameworks.

Theme	Related provisions in policy and legislation
Definition	Section 2(x) of the Forest Act (2019): environmental services are the benefits derived from the forest ecosystem, including carbon service, biodiversity protection, watershed and water-cycle system, ecotourism, and other prescribed products, services, and benefits (GoN, 2019a). Forestry Sector Strategy (2016-2025): ecosystem services are the benefits provided by healthy functioning ecosystems, including soil conservation, water conservation, biodiversity, carbon sequestration, flood control, climate regulation, aesthetic value, and others (p. xiii, MOFSC, 2016b).
Categories	The categories of ecosystem services, as outlined in the National Ramsar Strategy and Action Plan, Nepal (2018-2024) and the Nature Conservation National Strategic Framework for Sustainable Development (2015-2030), include: 1) provisioning services such as food, fodder, fuel, fiber, energy, clean water, and herbs; 2) regulating services such as water regulation, flood control, air quality maintenance, soil erosion prevention, climate regulation, pollination, and disease regulation; 3) supporting services such as soil formation, nutrient cycling, and habitat services; and 4) cultural services such as spiritual and religious value, aesthetic value, tourism and recreation, and research and education (MOFE, 2018; NPC, 2015).
Valuation methods	The Nature Conservation National Strategic Framework for Sustainable Development (2015–2030) recommends methods such as avoided cost, replacement cost, factor income, travel cost, hedonic pricing, and contingent valuation for valuing and accounting for ecosystem goods and services (NPC, 2015).

Nepal’s protected area policies acknowledge all four categories of ecosystem services: provisioning, regulating, supporting, and cultural. Of these, supporting and cultural services receive the greatest emphasis. This reflects both the foundational importance of species and habitat conservation in early protected areas and the strong cultural and tourism values associated with sites like Chitwan, known for its wildlife tourism, and Langtang, valued for its religious significance. The findings highlight that global initiatives, particularly the MEA (2005) and TEEB study (2010), have strongly influenced the integration of ecosystem services into Nepal’s post-2010 policies. These global initiatives have provided both the rationale and structure for embedding ecosystem service values into national conservation policies.

In parallel, ecosystem disservices—including fires, disease risks, and conservation-related restrictions—lack a formal legal definition and are narrowly framed

as human–wildlife conflict. A comprehensive recognition of both nature’s benefits and burdens would help justify conservation investments by demonstrating net societal gains. Recent legal reforms have opened the door for infrastructure development within protected areas, provided specific conditions are met. Notable examples include the Working Procedure for Providing Land in Protected Areas to Construct Infrastructure (2024) and an amendment to the National Parks and Wildlife Conservation Act (1973)—later annulled by the Supreme Court—which had allowed greater development flexibility. However, these changes have sparked strong criticism from academics, conservationists, and INGO representatives, who contend that the reforms increasingly favor corporate interests and commercial conservation models, often at the expense of local communities who face growing risks from human–wildlife conflict and reduced access to natural resources.

Policy recommendations

Ecosystem (dis)services can significantly influence how people perceive, access, and interact with protected areas, shaping their motivations, behaviors, and levels of engagement. However, these complex dynamics are seldom explicitly addressed in Nepal's protected area policies. Integrating an ecosystem (dis)service perspective into the policies is crucial for managing the reciprocal relationship between people and nature. Doing so can strengthen the legitimacy, equity, and long-term effectiveness of conservation efforts by fostering more inclusive and sustained community participation. Drawing on the research findings, the following policy recommendations aim to guide such integration in Nepal's protected area governance.

- 1) Explicitly incorporate ecosystem (dis)services into the core legal instruments governing protected areas:** Amend foundational legal frameworks—such as the National Parks and Wildlife Conservation Act (1973), its regulations (1974), and related policies—to explicitly include ecosystem (dis)services. This will provide a legal basis for integrating an ecosystem (dis)services perspective into the planning and management of national parks, wildlife reserves, hunting reserves, and conservation areas.
- 2) Promote non-monetary assessment of ecosystem (dis)services in the protected areas:** Current policy frameworks lack explicit provisions for the valuation and accounting for ecosystem (dis)services. Although monetary assessments can provide useful insights, they remain controversial, especially in societies that attribute intrinsic value to nature (Hummel et al., 2019). Reflecting this perspective, most studies in protected areas adopt non-monetary assessment

methods (Pu et al., 2023). Consequently, integrating a diverse range of non-monetary approaches—such as questionnaires, participatory mapping, social media analysis, scenario simulations, the Delphi method, social learning, social values for ecosystem services, multi-criteria decision analysis, and Bayesian belief networks (Márquez et al., 2023)—into policy frameworks would be both appropriate and effective.

- 3) Formalize the provision of carbon sequestration services:** While national policies—such as the Environment Protection Act (2019), Environment Protection Regulation (2020), Forest Act (2019), and Forest Regulation (2022)—provide explicit provisions for carbon sequestration services, core legal instruments governing protected areas remain silent on these services. This gap limits the ability to leverage protected areas—which cover nearly one-third of the country—for climate finance opportunities. It is recommended to amend foundational legal frameworks, including the National Parks and Wildlife Conservation Act (1973), its regulations (1974), and related policies—to recognize and enable carbon sequestration services explicitly. This would establish a legal basis for tapping into global carbon markets, positioning protected areas as key contributors to national and global climate goals and as potential revenue sources—especially important given existing restrictions on commercial use of resources such as timber and herbs.
- 4) Discourage commercial conservation models that marginalize local and indigenous communities:** While integrating ecosystem services into protected area policies offers new

opportunities, it also carries the risk of encouraging commercial conservation models. These models may prioritize profit-driven interests, potentially leading to elite resource capture and the marginalization of indigenous and local communities—raising serious environmental justice concerns. Therefore, policy integration must proceed with caution, ensuring that the rights, knowledge, and livelihoods of indigenous and local communities are upheld and prioritized over commercial interests.

- 5) Establish a national ecosystem accounting system using the UN SEEA ecosystem accounting framework:** The National Statistics Office should take the lead in formalizing and institutionalizing national ecosystem accounting system by implementing the UN's System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA) Ecosystem Accounting Framework. This system will enable systematic and periodic assessment of ecosystem services supplied by natural ecosystems. It will align ecosystem service data with national accounting structures, such as GDP, and support informed policy and decision-making processes.

Further information

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